

MENDEL: Overview of the Capabilities for Inventory and Source term generation

Aimé Tsilanizara¹, Rémi Baron², Tan-Dat Huynh¹, Sébastien Lahaye^{1,*}

¹Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service d'Études des Réacteurs et de Mathématiques Appliquées, 91191, Gif-sur-Yvette, France;

²Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service de Génie Logiciel pour la Simulation, 91191, Gif-sur-Yvette, France

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803958

ABSTRACT

MENDEL is the French new generation spent nuclear fuel inventory code dedicated to fuel cycle, structure activation and waste management studies. It is developed at CEA (Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives) with the support of EDF (Électricité de France) and Framatome.

MENDEL solves Bateman's generalized equations to compute the temporal evolution of isotopic concentrations. From those concentrations, other quantities of interest (QoI) for fuel cycle and waste management are computed. These QoI are activities, isotopic masses, decay heat, α , β , γ particle spectra, neutron spectra from spontaneous fission, (α ,n) or (γ ,n) reactions and radiotoxicity.

MENDEL implements a collection of numerical solvers, in a modern and flexible software architecture. As a result, these solvers are directly used inside APOLLO3[®] and TRIPOLI-4[®] to deal with fuel depletion. Other MENDEL capabilities such as the photon source and spectra determination are used by TRIPOLI-4[®].

From now on, MENDEL is considered to be the successor to DARWIN/PEPIN2 as it covers all DARWIN/PEPIN2's capacities while having some new functionalities. It is designed to be used in industrial and research applications. MENDEL is a multi-purpose code, computing isotopic concentrations for any nuclear fuel in operation, any material irradiated by a neutron flux as well as waste management. Regarding the reactor types addressed, applications for Pressurized Water Reactors (PWR), Sodium Fast Reactors (SFR), and Molten Salt Reactors (MSR) have already been processed.

This article provides an overview of MENDEL capabilities, emphasizing its advances comparatively to DARWIN/PEPIN2.

Keywords: Fuel cycle, simulation code, MENDEL, Validation process

1. INTRODUCTION

Fuel cycle codes aim to compute as precisely as possible the solution of Generalized Bateman equations [1] in order to obtain isotopic densities. From those densities will be computed other QoI such as decay heat, activities, radiotoxicity, nuclide masses or particle spectra. The Bateman equation reads:

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt}(t) = -(\lambda_i + \tau_{ii}) N_i(t) + \sum_{j \neq i} (b_{ji} \lambda_j + \tau_{ji}^{RR}) N_j(t) + \sum_k \gamma_{ki} \tau_k^f N_k(t) \quad (1)$$

where $N_i(t)$ stands for the concentration of isotope i at time t , λ_i is the decay constant of isotope i , τ_{ii} its disappearance rate, b_{ji} the decay branching ratio between isotopes j and i , τ_{ji}^{RR} the neutron induced reaction rate from isotope j to isotope i , k the list of fissile isotopes, γ_{ki} the independent fission yields

*sebastien.lahaye@cea.fr

from fissile system k to fission product i and τ_k^f the fission reaction rate of fissile system k . A fissile system is defined with the fissile isotope and the incident neutron energy range (thermal, fast or high energy, as specified in nuclear data evaluation files).

The accuracy on isotopic densities is of utmost importance for all other QoI.

CEA has a long history of codes computing isotopic depletion and cooling, for fuel cycle studies in reactors, structure activation or waste management. Most of those codes are used in CEA but also by its industrial partners or clients. We can cite fuel cycle codes DARWIN/PEPIN2 [2] and CESAR [3], but also neutron transport codes like APOLLO2 [4], CRONOS2 [5], ECCO [6] or ERANOS [7] embarking their own depletion solvers.

DARWIN/PEPIN2 can be seen as an equivalent to the American code ORIGEN [8] and its derivatives, or British FISPACT [9], with no limitations for the isotopes followed, as long as users provide isotopic evolution chains and nuclear data.

In the last decade, in the process of improving its calculation tools, CEA implemented MENDEL, its new generation code for depletion and cooling. From its version 3.2, released in 2024, it has equivalent capability with DARWIN/PEPIN2 for both nominal computations and uncertainty quantification (UQ) aspects.

DARWIN/PEPIN2 was designed with three main purposes: PWR fuel cycle computations, activation of structure under a neutron flux and decay only for nuclear waste management.

MENDEL is a multi-purpose code: it computes isotopic concentrations for any nuclear fuel in operation, any material activated or irradiated by a neutron flux, as well as any radioactive waste management. Nuclear fuel depletion and material activation use the same Bateman equations solvers, with potentially different depletion chains. Applications to PWR [10] and SFR [11] fuel cycles have been published. MENDEL can also solve the Bateman equation involving matter exchange coupling terms between several materials. Each material is linked to neighbours by exchange of isotopes, as encountered in MSR facilities.

During cooling phase, eventually following depletion or activation, MENDEL computes isotopic concentrations and the other QoI. MENDEL can also propagate the uncertainties due to nuclear data to most of those QoI: isotopic concentrations, decay heat, activities and particle spectra.

In this paper, we describe the main features of MENDEL, its general structure, its applications, and focus on its advances comparatively to DARWIN/PEPIN2.

2. MENDEL: SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE AND ORGANIZATION

2.1. Architecture and links to CEA neutron transport codes

MENDEL has been developed using the C++ object-oriented language with three main components linked one to another:

- MDLSOLVER library implements all the functions required to solve the Bateman equation: Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE) solvers, data models for depletion chains and reaction rates;
- MDLCYCLE library provides all the methods needed to calculate the nuclear fuel, irradiated material and radioactive waste QoI deduced from isotopic concentrations;
- MDLUSECASE library manages MENDEL standalone user interface. It provides all the user needs to perform calculations.

As part of the development of the CEA new generation neutron transport codes, it was decided to rationalize the Bateman equation solvers. MENDEL therefore shares its MDLSOLVER component with APOLLO3[®] [12], TRIPOLI-4[®] [13] and TRIPOLI-5[®] [14], and even more for TRIPOLI-4[®] since it also uses the MDLCYCLE component to evaluate decay photon sources, for example. Hence, MENDEL is

both a standalone code and a provider of services for CEA's deterministic and Monte-Carlo neutronics codes.

MENDEL standalone code is the result of compilations and links between these three components.

In this paper, we focus on the MENDEL standalone code.

2.2. MENDEL's user interface

MENDEL has two types of user interfaces:

- An ASCII interface where all the options are available through *keyword = values ASCII files*, where users define macro-functions to define the different objects (for example isotopic chain, nuclear data library or irradiation history) before running the computations.
- A **Python interface** is also available. It is obtained by wrapping the C++ language into Python for the three main components and has a different degree of maturity depending on the component. The use of Python interface offers an advantage over the previous one as it makes it easier to create a more complex calculation scheme, including loop structures, for example.

2.3. Nuclear and neutronic data for MENDEL

The nuclear data available with MENDEL's package can be described by dividing them into:

- All nuclear constant data (like half-lives, decay energies, independent fission yields, branching ratios or emitted α and γ rays) are provided in a unique HDF5 format file, named MENDEL Nuclear Constant Data library. This library gives nuclear constant data for several nuclear data evaluations: JEFF-3.1.1, ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0 and JENDL-4.0.
- A set of multi-group cross sections files (GENDF format) are available for several nuclear data evaluations, several neutron-incident energetic meshes and several temperatures. Each file provides data for one isotope, so that different data sources can be selected for different isotopes in a calculation, mainly if users want to evaluate the impact of a new nuclear data evaluation on a given isotope. The mix is possible through an explicit option (*exception file*).
- Depletion chains are provided in ASCII file format. Users can adjust the chains. Three *complete* chains are given with MENDEL package (one containing all reactions described in the nuclear data evaluation, one focused on nuclear fuel isotopes and reactions and one focused on radioactive decay only). Shorter chains can be defined and used.

Table I summarises the origins of the data available for the latest version 3.2 of the code. The neutronic

Data Libraries	Evaluation origins
Nuclear Constant Data	ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/BVIII.0, JENDL-4.0 CEA evaluations: CEAv5.1.2 and CEAv6 (based on JEFF-3.1.1)
Cross sections	EAF2003, EAF2010, ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/BVIII.0, JENDL-4.0 CEAv5.1.2 (based on JEFF-3.1.1) and CEAv6 (based on JEFF-3.2)
Depletion Chains	EAF2003, EAF2010, ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/BVIII.0, JENDL-4.0 CEAv5.1.2 (based on JEFF-3.1.1) and CEAv6 (based on JEFF-3.2)

Table I. Evaluations available in MENDEL per data type

data such as neutron flux and self-shielded cross sections are input data for MENDEL. The code is able to read them from input files in three formats:

- APOLLO2's Saphyb file (HDF5 or XSM format) contains neutron fluxes, initial nuclide concentrations and self-shielded cross sections for any region to be depleted or irradiated.
- APOLLO3[®]'s MPO file (HDF5 format) contains neutron fluxes, initial nuclide concentrations and

self-shielded cross sections for any region to be depleted or irradiated.

- INTERPEP file (ASCII format) contains neutron fluxes and initial nuclide concentrations, while self-shielded cross sections can be given in XML format. Those files are historically generated by TRIPOLI-4[®] and ERANOS. Being ASCII files, they can easily be generated by any other reactor physics code willing to use MENDEL for fuel cycle and waste management studies.

As MENDEL is intended to be the successor to DARWIN/PEPIN2, nuclear and neutronic data in known DARWIN/PEPIN2 formats can also be used. This makes it easy for users to make the transition.

2.4. Verification and Validation process

MENDEL's development is based on a strong Verification and Validation process.

DARWIN/PEPIN2 being a fully qualified code for PWR applications, part of the validation on PWR has been done comparing the results of MENDEL and DARWIN/PEPIN2 when reproducing the numerical options of DARWIN/PEPIN2.

Concerning the Verification part, a solid non-regression test suite is launched regularly on all supported Linux and Windows platforms. Supported Linux platforms include RedHat-like, Debian-like and Ubuntu Operating Systems. The tests aim to use MENDEL's functionalities with multiple options.

Some tests are based on numerical benchmarks or experimental data (mostly on decay and Post Irradiation Examination (PIE) concentrations) and constitute the Numerical Validation part of the process. Part of this work has been published, including PWR PIE on concentrations [10, 15] and decay heat [16].

2.5. Nuclear data uncertainties propagation in MENDEL

Nuclear data uncertainties can be propagated in MENDEL to most of the expected responses : isotopic concentration, activity, decay heat and emitted particle spectra. Input uncertainties are associated to radioactive decay half-lives, decay energies, branching ratios (decay and neutronic reaction), independent fission yields, multigroup cross sections, intensities of particle spectra emitted by decay (α , γ). Three approaches are implemented:

- Following what was implemented in DARWIN/PEPIN2 through the INCERD [2] package, a **first order direct perturbation method** (One At a Time) is available. This method supposes a *small perturbation* approach, but it is accurate enough for macroscopic data like decay heat, as shown with all comparisons done.
- A **stochastic propagation** is also available, where correlated samples can be generated either directly by MENDEL or by specific tools. We provide scripts for sampling with CEA's software URANIE [17]. Comparisons between deterministic and stochastic approaches are an essential point for the verification of uncertainty quantification methodologies [10, 16].
- More recently, a new calculation scheme based on generalized perturbation theory (**GPT**) has been implemented with APOLLO3[®] and MENDEL [18] to handle the sensitivity calculation of isotopic concentration and decay heat to nuclear data. It will be available with the next MENDEL version.

We show in Figure 1 an example of Validation process on a PWR PIE [19] using CEA v5.1.2 nuclear data with comparison of actinides and fission products concentration values. Both DARWIN/PEPIN2 and MENDEL use neutron fluxes issued from an APOLLO2 neutronic's calculation. Vertical bars correspond to associated uncertainties (experimental and uncertainty quantification). DARWIN stands for DARWIN/PEPIN2 in the figures. In Figure 2, we show a Validation process for the CEA's MERCI experiment [16], computing decay heat on short cooling times after fuel discharge using CEA v5.1.2 nuclear data. MENDEL and DARWIN/PEPIN2 both use neutron fluxes issued from an APOLLO2 neutronic's calculation. DARWIN stands for DARWIN/PEPIN2 on the right Figure.

Figure 1. C/E ratio of MENDEL and DARWIN/PEPIN2 with uncertainty propagation within 1σ , PIE on isotopic concentrations for Actinides (left) and Fission products (right) [15].

Figure 2. Computation/Measurement ratio of MENDEL (left) and DARWIN/PEPIN2 (right) in red compared to $2\text{-}\sigma$ decay heat uncertainties due to nuclear data (grey area) [16].

3. DESCRIPTION OF THE FUNCTIONALITIES

3.1. Transition from DARWIN/PEPIN2 to MENDEL

Users can easily switch from the old to the new generation of code, with the ability to reproduce its results. Indeed, from MENDEL version 3.2, all the capabilities of DARWIN/PEPIN2.4.8 (both released in 2024), are available in MENDEL. Then, DARWIN/PEPIN2 has entered in a maintenance stage, meaning that all new functionalities will now be written only in MENDEL.

MENDEL version 3.2 can reproduce the same options as DARWIN/PEPIN2 (fuel irradiation, fissile or non fissile material activation, decay). The power history (evolution of the reactor power in operation) defined for MENDEL depletion calculation may be identical or different to the one used to calculate the neutron flux in the input files (Saphyb/MPO/INTERPEP), like in DARWIN/PEPIN2.

Users can freely choose between the collection of Bateman equations solvers which have been implemented (Runge-Kutta, CRAM and Analytic solution [20]). Analytical solver, already existing in DARWIN/PEPIN2 for cooling and waste management, has been extended to any triangular depletion matrix, something already possible in CRONOS2. Runge-Kutta 4th order method dealing with unsaturated predicted isotopes is available, as it is already the case with DARWIN/PEPIN2 and APOLLO2.

Furthermore, other solvers were introduced, like CRAM [21] or MENDEL's original Hybrid Approach [20].

3.2. MENDEL's new capabilities

Compared to DARWIN/PEPIN2, a number of improvements appear with MENDEL:

- New links with APOLLO3[®] with the MPO file which replaces the APOLLO2's Saphyb.
- All reactor types are now directly and easily computed, including MSR thanks to a new functionality which manages the exchange between depleted media during the irradiation.
- Fuel depletion and material activation are no longer separate branches, using the same numerical approaches and the same data (for neutron flux and microscopic cross sections).
- Nuclear data can be easily modified and the introduction of a new nuclear data evaluation does not require any change on the code. Users can mix cross sections from different evaluations at their own risk.
- The determination of the formation pathways of the nuclides of interest (formerly INVERSION package in DARWIN/PEPIN2) has been deeply improved in MENDEL. For example, the following lines give the predominant production ways of La140 in a PWR fuel pellet:

Effective list of ways of production of LA140 (without loops), organized
by decreasing contribution:
Total = 99.1691% of LA140 final concentration.

```
(1) 21.9% LA140 <-(d|b-) BA140 <-(d|b-) CS140 <-(n,f) PU239 <-(d|b-) NP239 <-(d|b-) U239 <-(n,g) U238
(2) 18.9% LA140 <-(d|b-) BA140 <-(d|b-) CS140 <-(d|b-) XE140 <-(n,f) U235
(3) 12.9% LA140 <-(d|b-) BA140 <-(d|b-) CS140 <-(d|b-) XE140 <-(n,f) PU239 <-(d|b-) NP239 <-(d|b-) U239
    <-(n,g) U238
(4) 10.7% LA140 <-(d|b-) BA140 <-(d|b-) CS140 <-(n,f) U235
(5) 8.62% LA140 <-(d|b-) BA140 <-(d|b-) CS140 <-(d|b-) XE140 <-(n,f) PU241 <-(n,g) PU240 <-(n,g) PU239
    <-(d|b-) NP239 <-(d|b-) U239 <-(n,g) U238
(6) 6.93% LA140 <-(d|b-) BA140 <-(n,f) PU239 <-(d|b-) NP239 <-(d|b-) U239 <-(n,g) U238
(...)
```

- UQ has been extended to stochastic and GPT approaches.

Some completely new functionalities are also offered:

- The solution to Bateman's adjoint equation is available with MENDEL.
- Reaction rates (RR) can be considered constant or time-dependent during each burnup step. Time-dependent RR is computed by linear or parabolic interpolation. This new possibility enables to reproduce the APOLLO3[®] and APOLLO2 predictor/corrector schemes, and to improve accuracy when widening the burnup steps in fuel cycle studies.
- Reaction branching ratio are no longer fixed but can be computed on the fly. This implies the end of the neutron-spectrum and energy-mesh dependent isotopic chains present in DARWIN/PEPIN2.
- Users can now choose between several solvers and solver options. A default choice is given.

3.3. Perspectives

The transition from DARWIN/PEPIN2 to MENDEL is now fully possible. This milestone was of utmost importance for the current users of DARWIN/PEPIN2, in CEA but also in the French nuclear industry.

Two major developments are now opened.

On one hand, MENDEL standalone code will continue to improve its capabilities, in order to ensure a transition from other inventory codes to a new generation represented by MENDEL. In the near future, MENDEL will offer functionalities required for industrial codes, such as speed of execution combined with results accuracy. These features will be based on effective interpolations of a collection of pre-tabulated neutron fluxes and self-shielded cross sections.

On the other hand, at the same time, new fuel cycle options will be defined using MENDEL instead of DARWIN/PEPIN2. This will make a transition towards DARWIN3 [22], the future CEA's com-

prehensive modeling and simulation suite for Spent Nuclear Fuel characterization which will embark APOLLO3[®], TRIPOLI-4[®], TRIPOLI-5[®] and MENDEL. Whereas DARWIN2 was mainly PWR-oriented, DARWIN3 will address all kinds of reactors.

4. CONCLUSIONS

From MENDEL version 3.2, released in 2024, MENDEL has equivalent capability with DARWIN/PEPIN2. It is also linked into APOLLO3[®] and TRIPOLI-4[®] to ensure precise calculations of isotopic concentrations. It makes it possible to do an in-code depletion for Monte Carlo reactor physics computations, which was not possible directly with DARWIN/PEPIN2. For deterministic neutronics options, the use of MENDEL solver enables to reproduce in APOLLO3[®] the predictor corrector schemes already present in APOLLO2, and most of the solvers implemented in the previous generation codes are implemented in MENDEL.

Previous computation options DARWIN2, which is using ECCO/ERANOS and APOLLO2 with DARWIN/PEPIN2, will be replaced in the next future by DARWIN3, using APOLLO3[®], TRIPOLI-4[®] and MENDEL with adequate neutronics options and nuclear data evaluation.

Concerning the iso-capability with DARWIN/PEPIN2, one needs to note that all input data libraries (neutron flux, nuclear constant, cross sections) readable by DARWIN/PEPIN2 are also readable by MENDEL. This was done specifically to facilitate the transition of DARWIN/PEPIN2 users to MENDEL.

MENDEL deals with some MSRs specific features, which include isotope exchanges during operation.

MENDEL is already answering both industrial and research applications needs, and has begun to be used by French research institutes and industrials R&D teams of the nuclear reactor field. It meets the needs for fuel cycle and waste management, material activation or source determination for shielding applications.

Further developments are planned to assess and improve the use of pre-computed reaction rates data bases, thereby making available in DARWIN3 all functionalities needed for both research and industrial applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank EDF and Framatome for their invaluable support in the development of the MENDEL code.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Bateman. "The solution of a system of Differential Equations Occuring in the Theory of Radioactive Transformations." *Proc Cambridge Philosophical Society*, **volume 15**, pp. 423–427 (1910).
- [2] A. Tsilanizara and T.-D. Huynh. "New feature of DARWIN/PEPIN2 inventory code: Propagation of nuclear data uncertainties to decay heat and nuclide density." *Ann of Nucl Energy*, **volume 164** (2021).
- [3] J.-M. Vidal, R. Eschbach, A. Launay, C. Binet, J.-F. Thro, et al. "CESAR5.3: an industrial tool for nuclear fuel and waste characterization with associated qualification." In *WM2012 Conf.* (2012).
- [4] R. Sanchez et al. "APOLLO2 year 2010." *Nucl Eng Tech*, **volume 42(5)**, pp. 474–499 (2010).
- [5] J.-J. Lautard, S. Loubière, and C. Fedon-Magnaud. "CRONOS: a modular computational system for neutronic core calculations." In *Specialists meeting on advanced calculational methods for power reactors*, pp. 42–50. Cadarache, France (1990).

- [6] G. Rimpault. "Algorithmic features of the ECCO cell code for treating heterogeneous fast reactor subassemblies." In *Proc. Int. Topl. Mtg. on Reactor Phys. and Comp.* Portland, USA (1995).
- [7] J.-M. Ruggieri, J. Tommasi, J.-F. Lebrat, C. Suteau, D. Plisson-Rieunier, C. De Saint Jean, G. Rimpault, and J.-C. Sublet. "ERANOS 2.1: International code system for GEN IV fast reactor analysis." In *Proc. of ICAPP*, volume 6, pp. 2432–2439. Reno, NV, USA (2006).
- [8] S. Ludwig and A. Croff. "ORIGEN2. 2–Isotope Generation and Depletion Code Matrix Exponential Method." Technical Report CCC-0371, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (2002).
- [9] J.-Ch Sublet et al. "FISPACT-II: An Advanced Simulation System for Activation, Transmutation and Material Modelling." *Nuclear Data Sheets*, **volume 139**, pp. 77–137 (2017).
- [10] S. Lahaye, J. Luo, P. Bellier, T.-D. Huynh, and A. Tsilanizara. "Uncertainty quantification of isotopic densities in depleted fuel." In *ANS Best Estimate Plus Uncertainty Int. Conf. (BEPU 2018)* (2018).
- [11] S. Lahaye, A. Tsilanizara, T.-D. Huynh, R. Baron, and R. Okuyama. "MENDEL-based Fuel Cycle Analysis for Sodium Fast Reactors." In *ANS Winter Meeting 2025* (2025).
- [12] P. Mosca, L. Bourhrara, A. Calloo, A. Gammicchia, F. Goubioud, L. Mao, F. Madiot, F. Malouch, E. Masiello, F. Moreau, et al. "APOLLO3: Overview of the new code capabilities for reactor physics analysis." *Nuc Sci and Eng*, **volume 199**(sup1), pp. S17–S30 (2025).
- [13] F. Hugot, A. Jinaphanh, C. Jouanne, C. Larmier, Y.-K. Lee, D. Mancusi, O. Petit, T. Visonneau, and A. Zoia. "Overview of the TRIPOLI-4 Monte Carlo code, version 12." *EPJ Nuclear Sci Technol*, **volume 10**, p. 17 (2024).
- [14] D. Mancusi, E. Brun, B. Dechenaux, K. Fröhlicher, T. Gonçalves, A. Jinaphanh, M. Kowalski, C. Larmier, F. Malvagi, G. Millasseau, et al. "Overview of TRIPOLI-5, a Monte Carlo code for HPC." *EPJ N-Nuclear Sciences & Technologies*, **volume 10**, p. 26 (2024).
- [15] S. Lahaye, P. Bellier, H. Mao, A. Tsilanizara, and Y. Kawamoto. "First Verification and Validation Steps of MENDEL Release V1.0 Cycle Code System." In *PHYSOR 2014* (2014). Kyoto, Japan.
- [16] S. Lahaye, T.-D. Huynh, A. Tsilanizara, J.-C. Jaboulay, and S. Bourganel. "Comparisons between a priori Uncertainty Quantification and Calculation/Measurement Discrepancies Applied to the MERCI UO₂ Fuel Rod Decay Heat Experiment." In *ANS Winter Meet. 2016*. Las Vegas, USA (2016).
- [17] F. Gaudier. "URANIE : The CEA/DEN Uncertainty and Sensitivity platform." In *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, volume 2 (6) (2010).
- [18] N. Linden, A. Tsilanizara, and J. Tommasi. "Depletion Perturbation Theory in decay heat calculation context." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 185**, p. 109743 (2023).
- [19] A. Sasahara, T. Matsumura, G. Nicolau, and Y. Kiyanagi. "Isotopic analysis of actinides and fission products in LWR high-burnup UO₂ spent fuels and its comparison with nuclide composition calculated using JENDL, ENDF/B, JEF and JEFF." *J Nucl Sci Tech*, **volume 45**(4), pp. 313–327 (2008).
- [20] S. Lahaye, A. Anne, R. Baron, T.-D. Huynh, and A. Tsilanizara. "New Bateman Equation Solvers in MENDEL Version 3.1." In *ICNC 2023* (2023). Sendai, Japan.
- [21] M. Pusa and J. Leppänen. "An efficient implementation of the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) for solving the burnup equations." In *PHYSOR 2012*. Knoxville, USA (2012).
- [22] C. Vaglio-Gaudard, P. Bellier, L. Buiron, S. Lahaye, J.-F. Lebrat, P. Miranda, B. Roque, and A. Tsilanizara. "Development of the DARWIN3-SFR fuel cycle tool for decay heat calculations in new generation fast reactors." In *PHYSOR 2016*. Sun Valley, USA (2016).